

Assessment of the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among patients age greater than or equal to 18 years presented with musculoskeletal pain in selected public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health Bureau, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vitamin D deficiency is a significant global public health concern, crucial for healthy bones, immunity, and general well-being. Affecting an estimated one billion people worldwide, Vitamin D deficiency can lead to severe bone disorders, increased fracture risk, and chronic diseases. Often underdiagnosed and undertreated, it necessitates targeted public health interventions.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the prevalence and associated factors of Vitamin D deficiency among adult patients (≥ 18 years) presenting with musculoskeletal pain in public hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, in 2025.

Methods: An institutional-based cross-sectional study was conducted in three randomly selected Addis Ababa public hospitals. A total of 385 proportionally allocated participants were chosen via systematic random sampling. Descriptive statistics and multivariable regression analyses (95% CI, $p < 0.05$) were employed.

Results: The overall prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency among adult respondents with musculoskeletal pain was 68.1% (95% CI: 63.1%–72.7%). Multivariable analysis identified age, urban residency, and marital status (single/widowed versus divorced) as significant factors. Respondents aged over sixty years were four times more likely to have Vitamin D deficiency than those aged 18–40 years (AOR = 4.412). Urban residents were three and half times more likely to be deficient than rural residents (AOR = 3.580).

Conclusion and Recommendations: Vitamin D deficiency is prevalent among adult patients with musculoskeletal pain in Addis Ababa. These findings underscore the critical need for increased awareness, routine screening, and targeted interventions, particularly for older adults and urban dwellers, to improve musculoskeletal health and overall well-being.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Musculoskeletal, Public Hospital, prevalence, Addis Ababa, cross-sectional study.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to a 2020 systematic review in the USA, vitamin D, a fat-soluble vitamin, facilitates calcium and phosphorus absorption in the gut, supporting bone mineralization, growth, remodeling, and maintaining serum calcium and phosphate levels (1). Beyond bone health, vitamin D regulates many cellular functions as most nucleated cells express the vitamin D receptor (VDR). About 10–20% of requirements come from diet, mainly fatty fish, egg yolk, and fortified foods (2). Vitamin D exists as D₂ (ergocalciferol, from molds) and D₃ (cholecalciferol, synthesized in skin upon sunlight exposure) (3).

Serum 25(OH)D below 30 nmol/L, the best marker of vitamin D status, indicates insufficiency (4). Multiple risk factors affect vitamin D levels, including age, sex, obesity, socioeconomic status, chronic illness, fractures, diet, clothing, skin color, ethnicity, latitude, culture, limited outdoor activity, and season (5). Globally, about 15.7% of adults are deficient (25(OH)D <30 nmol/L) (6).

A 2019 systematic review in Africa showed prevalence ranging from 30–80%, with pooled prevalence at 17.3%. Causes include urbanization, cultural practices, and poor diet (7). In Ethiopia, deficiency is also a major concern: a 2022 study in Addis Ababa found 50–70% prevalence, higher in urban populations due to reduced sunlight exposure and indoor work (8).

Vitamin D deficiency contributes to proximal muscle weakness, bone pain, and osteomalacia, often underdiagnosed in clinical practice (9). Raising awareness, early screening, and prevention can improve musculoskeletal health and reduce burden (10). However, most Ethiopian studies focus on children, with limited research among adults with musculoskeletal pain (8, 11–13). Thus, this study aims to assess prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among adults with musculoskeletal pain in Addis Ababa.

1.1. Statement of problem

Vitamin D deficiency is a major public health problem causing rickets in children and osteomalacia, osteoporosis, fractures, infections, autoimmune diseases, cardiovascular disorders, depression, cognitive decline, and certain cancers in adults (14–16). Prevention through sunlight, fortified foods, and supplementation is possible, yet awareness remains low. In Ethiopia, 56% of mothers had good knowledge and 55.6% practiced proper sunlight exposure, with regional variations—54.4% in Amhara vs. 58.3% in Sidama—due to education, cultural, and informational differences (17,18). Despite interventions, deficiency affects 50–70% of adults, especially in urban areas with less sun exposure (8). Musculoskeletal pain is a common presentation, with supplementation crucial for management. One study reported deficiency in 41.9% of adults with back pain, fatigue, or generalized pain (8). Most research in Ethiopia centers on children (8,11–13). Therefore, this study aims to assess the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among adults with musculoskeletal pain in Addis Ababa public hospitals.

1.2. Objective

1.2.1 General objective

- To assess the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among adult patients presented with musculoskeletal pain in public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2025.

1.2.2 Specific objective

- To determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among adult patients presented with musculoskeletal pain in public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2025.
- To identify factors of vitamin D deficiency among adult patients presented with musculoskeletal pain in public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2025.

1.3. Significance of study

The findings indicate that severe deficiency of vitamin D is significantly associated with the presence of chronic widespread pain, but it does not play a major independent triple role-highlight in predicting regional musculoskeletal pain. This highlights the importance of further research in this area and suggests that people with low vitamin D levels are more likely to experience widespread pain via musculoskeletal system which can impact negatively on their quality of life. (17)

The recognition that vitamin D deficiency is prevalent in the general population and may contribute to chronic pain supports public health recommendations including education and awareness-raising, dietary intake promotion, safe sun exposure as well as food fortification on occasion or recommendation for supplementation aimed at raising levels of 25(OH)D within populations. This is even more critical in regions with limited sunlight due to the higher deficiency rate.(8)

Even if there are a lot of adult patients visiting public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau, limited studies are done to assess the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency in adult patients presented with musculoskeletal pain.(13, 16) As a result, this study is aimed to assess the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among adult patients presented with musculoskeletal pain in selected public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Vitamin d deficiency and its prevalence

Vitamin D deficiency is recognized as a widespread global health concern, affecting populations across diverse regions. A cross-sectional study in Yemen highlighted its prevalence worldwide, particularly in South Asia, the Middle East, North Africa, Europe, and the United States, where it is largely underdiagnosed due to cultural, environmental, and lifestyle factors (19). Similarly, a meta-analysis in the Middle East, China, Mongolia, and India confirmed that high-risk groups such as children, pregnant women, older adults, and non-Western immigrants are disproportionately affected (20). A systematic review conducted by Cui et al. revealed that between 2000 and 2022, 15.7% of people had serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels below 30 nmol/L, indicating that many individuals face health risks associated with low vitamin D (6).

In Africa, the problem is equally concerning. A South African study found that 28.5% of health workers were vitamin D deficient, particularly black Africans and those older than 42 years, with strong associations to obesity, diabetes, and metabolic syndrome (9). In Cameroon, prevalence was 10.2% (21), while in Uganda, 40.2% of pregnant women had serum vitamin D levels below 20 ng/mL (22).

Evidence from Ethiopia shows a particularly high burden despite abundant sunshine. A retrospective cross-sectional study found widespread deficiency in patients with non-specific neuromuscular pain and fatigue (3). In Sodo town, 39% of pregnant women were affected (23), while a case-control study in northwest Ethiopia reported 46.2% prevalence overall and 61.5% among tuberculosis patients (24). In Addis Ababa, vitamin D deficiency was found in 96% of patients with multiple sclerosis, with mean serum levels of only 14.8 ng/mL (11), and another study confirmed almost universal deficiency among patients with neuromuscular pain (3).

Several risk factors contribute to this high prevalence. Age and gender play important roles, with studies in Yemen and Thailand showing higher odds among women and younger adults who spend more time indoors (19,25). Other determinants include unemployment, low fish consumption, and infrequent sun exposure as reported in Egypt (26). Additional factors identified in a systematic review include poor diet, malabsorption disorders, liver and pancreatic disease, bariatric surgery, and obesity, which reduces vitamin D bioavailability (27). Urban residence and higher education have also been linked to deficiency due to indoor work patterns and lifestyle differences compared to rural populations (4).

The clinical implications of vitamin D deficiency are wide-ranging. Low levels compromise brain function, leading to memory loss, dementia, depression, and poor recovery after injury (28). They are also associated with chronic inflammation and cardiovascular diseases (29), increased adiposity and low muscle mass in women (30), and worsened bone density loss, fractures, and osteoporosis in the elderly (31).

An important area of research is the relationship between vitamin D deficiency and musculoskeletal pain. Several studies have found that lower vitamin D levels are correlated with greater pain intensity, chronic widespread pain, and worse outcomes in osteoarthritis, particularly in weight-bearing joints (32–34). The prevalence of deficiency among adults with musculoskeletal pain is typically between 30% and 53% when using a threshold of <20 ng/mL, though estimates vary across populations and settings (35).

2.5. Theoretical and conceptual framework

FIGURE 1 PROPOSED CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK SHOWING THE FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AMONG PATIENTS PRESENTED WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL PAIN IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS UNDER ADDIS ABABA CITY ADMINISTRATION HEALTH BUREAU IN ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA, 2024; ADAPTED FROM REVIEW OF LITERATURES. (36–42)

3. METHOD

3.1. Study area and period

Addis Ababa, which serves as the political capital and the key commercial and cultural hub of Ethiopia, is situated geographically in the center of the country at a latitude of 9°2'N and a longitude of 38°45'E. The city has an average elevation of 2,400 meters above sea level, while the highest point, Entoto Hill, located to the north, reaches an elevation of 3,200 meters. It is divided into 11 subcities called kifle ketema and 116 woredas which are the lowest administrative units.

According to the 2007 Census carried out by the Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia (CSA), the population of Addis Ababa city is 3,384,569. The city is situated at an elevation of 7,546 feet (2,300 meters). The city has surface area of about 530.14 km². Languages spoken include Amharic (71.0%), Afaan Oromo (10.7%), Gurage (8.37%), Tigrigna (3.60%), Silt'e (1.82%) and Gamo (1.03%).(43) Projected Population Size of Addis Ababa in 2022 is 3,859,638).(44)

According to 2012 (EFY) Health and Health Related Indicators published by MoH, There are 49 hospitals,13 are public of which 6 are owned by Addis Ababa City administration health bureau, 5 NGOs, and 32 private,27 public health centers, and 130 public health stations,700 different levels of private clinics are found in Addis Ababa city administrative region.(45)

The research was conducted from November 2024 to July 2025 with a specific period for data collection, analysis, and reporting.

3.2. Study design

Institution-based cross sectional study was conducted.

3.3. Population

3.3.1. Target population

All patients older than or equal to 18 years with musculoskeletal pain in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

3.3.2. Source population

All patients older than or equal to 18 years with musculoskeletal pain who attended public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

3.3.3. Study population

Patients older than or equal to 18 years with musculoskeletal pain attended at selected public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, who meet the inclusion criteria and were available during the time of data collection.

3.4. Sampling unit

Patient

3.5. Study units/subject

Each patient older than or equal to 18 years with musculoskeletal pain whose vitamin D level and associated factors were assessed.

3.6. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

3.6.1. Inclusion criteria

All patients older than or equal to 18 years with musculoskeletal pain attended a selected public hospital under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau in Addis Ababa, who was participated in the study and available at the time of data collection.

3.6.2. Exclusion criteria

All Patients younger than 18 years and those unable to communicate (critically ill) were excluded from the study.

3.7. Operational definitions

- **Vitamin D levels as deficient** – when the serum level of vitamin D is less than 30ng/ml.(6,23,46).**Normal Vitamin D level** - when the serum level of vitamin D is greater than or equal to 30ng/ml(6,23,46)
- **Widespread (multiple sites) pain** - Pain present in at least 4 out of 5 body regions (shoulder girdle, upper arm, lower arm, hip (buttock, trochanter),upper leg, lower leg,jaw,neck,chest,abdomen,upper back and lower back) and the pain must include both sides of the body and be present above and below the waist.(49)
- **One Standard Drink Equivalent** =1 bottle/can of beer,1 glass of wine,1/2 glass/berele of Tej and 1-1.5 cups of Tella.(51–54)
- **Adherence to exercise for adults:** at least 30 minutes per session, and 150–300 minutes per week of moderate-intensity activity or 10 minutes per session, 75–150 minutes per week of vigorous-intensity activity.(55)
 - **Moderate intensity Activities:** Walking(3–4 mph),cycling (10–12 mph),washing windows, mopping),Dancing, Recreational swimming, basketball (non-competitive) ,Volleyball (non-competitive) and Gardening (digging, planting).(56–58)
 - **Vigorous intensity activities:** Running (5+ mph). and Jogging, Fast cycling (14–16 mph), cycling uphill, Competitive swimming, Competitive basketball or soccer, Hiking uphill ,Karate, kickboxing, or taekwondo and High-energy dance styles (e.g., hip-hop, salsa, or step aerobics). (56–58)
 - **Body mass index** is determined by dividing a person's weight in kilograms by the square of their height in meters. For adults over 20, BMI is categorized as below 18.5: Underweight, 18.5–24.9: Normal weight, 25.0–29.9: Overweight and 30.0 and above: Obese.(59)
 - **Adequate sunlight exposure:** is exposing the face, arms, and legs to sunlight for 10–30 minutes, 2–3/3-6 times per week, during midday (10 a.m. to 3 p.m.) with UV index ≥ 3 is sufficient to maintain adequate vitamin D levels for lighter skin tones (Fitzpatrick skin types I–III) and darker skin tones (Fitzpatrick skin types IV–VI) respectively.(60,61)

- **Fasting State** - Abstaining from all food and caloric beverages for a period of 8–12 hours. (64,65)
- **Lifestyle factors** - are modifiable behaviors and habits that influence an individual's health and well-being. These include diet, physical activity, smoking, alcohol consumption, and substance use.(72)
- **Nutritional deficiency** - when the body does not receive or absorb adequate amounts of essential nutrients, such as vitamins, minerals, proteins, fats, and carbohydrates, required for optimal functioning.(73)
- **Adequate milk consumption:** ≥ 2 cups /day and adequate fish consumption ≥ 3 times /week.(26)
- **Classification of smokers based on daily cigarette consumption:** 1. Light Smoker (1–10 cigarettes/day), 2. Moderate Smoker (11–20 cigarettes/day) 3. Heavy Smoker (21–29 cigarettes/day) and 4. Very Heavy/Chain Smoker (≥ 30 cigarettes/day).(80)

3.8. Sample size determination

For the first objective, sample size calculation was done by using the single population proportion formula separately. After comparing p – value for vitamin D deficiency in the previous similar studies, sample size was calculated by considering a p-value of 0.39.(23) Level of confidence of 95%, and margin of error 5%:

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = \frac{Z^2 * p * q}{d^2}$$

Where;

Z-level of significance which was 1.96

p - Proportion of patients who were vitamin D deficient

q- Proportion of patients who were not vitamin D deficient

d- Margin of error (0.05)

n0- Minimum sample size from infinite population

Substituting the values for each of these variables in the above formula, the sample size was estimated to be 366. Since my population was finite (6581) and $n_0/N = 366/6581 = 0.06$ which was $> 5\%$, the final sample size was $n = n_0/1 + n_0/N$. Where, n = the final sample size required and N = the total number of patients in the three selected hospitals who fulfill the inclusion criteria. Then, when we substitute the values our final sample size required was $n = n_0/1 + n_0/N = 366/1 + 366/6581 = 347$.

For the second objective, sample size calculation was done by using Open EPI info software package version number 3.1. The four factors such as age under 45 years, sunlight exposure < 30 minutes/day, being female and low consumers of fish and milk were significantly associated with the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency.

Since the sample size calculated for the second objective of low consumers of milk and fish was relatively large (350) and by considering 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was 385 for both populations.

3.9. Sampling technique/procedures

There are 12 public hospitals in Addis Ababa, 6 of them are under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau among those 3 hospitals (Yekatit 12 Medical College Hospital, Ras Desta Damtew Memorial Hospital and Menilik II Comprehensive Specialized Hospital) were selected using lottery method (simple random sampling). The study was conducted on the selected hospitals. The number of study units for each unit was proportionally allocated (based on the number of patients on that hospital) and those who were part of the final sample size were selected using systematic random sampling.

Public hospitals in Addis Ababa under
Addis Ababa city administration
health Bureau

FIGURE 2 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES OF PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AMONG PATIENTS WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL PAIN IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS UNDER ADDIS ABABA CITY ADMINISTRATION HEALTH BUREAU IN ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA, 2025.

3.10. Variables of the study

3.10.1. Dependent variable

Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency

3.10.2. Independent variables

Socio-demographic factors

- Age, sex, marital status, level of education, income, place of residence

Personal factors

- Co-morbidities like GI disorder(malabsorption), liver diseases & Bariatric surgery, Obesity & DM,CKD
- Medication like Anticonvulsants ,Anti-HIV Drugs and PPIs
- Pregnancy and lactation
- Smoking
- Alcohol

Life style factors

- Nutritional deficiency
- Physical inactivity
- Unemployment

Environmental factors

- sunlight exposure
- Geographical location

3.11. Data collection instruments

Data for vitamin D deficiency and associated factors was assessed by a tool containing a questionnaire, a clinical assessment form, and a laboratory data collection sheet through kobo toolbox, which were together ensure comprehensive data gathering. Semi-structured interviewer administered questionnaire was used. Since there were limited available standard questionnaires to assess prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and associated factors, it was prepared by the principal investigator from review of pertinent literatures.(4, 25, 32, 35). All the questions were prepared in English and were translated to the language of Amharic by experts who are fluent in

both language and back translated to English to see its consistency. Clinical Assessment, was Conducted by trained personnel using standardized equipment available at the facility. For the serum level of vitamin D, secondary data was taken from the patient card or laboratory registration. A record unit for serum vitamin D was consistently (ng/ml or nmol/L) as per study protocol.(11, 22, 31, 41)

3.12. Data collection methods

Data was collected by three trained qualified nurses who were assigned at each of the three selected hospitals and were supervised by one General medical practitioner (MD) at each respective hospital. The principal investigator was responsible for the overall management of the project; the development of the final questionnaire; securing participation of selected patients; identifying, training and assignment of data collectors. The purpose of the training was to ensure that all the data collectors should have the same information about the study instrument and followed the same interview procedures. The training was delt with the purpose of the study, confidentiality and how to approach and forward questions to clients.

3.13. Data quality assurance

Both the data collectors and supervisors were trained for one day in the objective and methodology of the research, data collection approach. The questionnaire was translated to Amharic language and back translated into English by another person to check for consistency. Pretest was conducted in 5% of the samples at Zewuditu Hospital. The data collection instrument was assessed for completeness, consistency, and applicability and was ratified accordingly. The study procedures were protected the patient's privacy by allowing anonymous and voluntary participation.

The Fast Alcohol Screening Test (FAST) – (Cronbach's alpha = 0.77; Test-retest reliability = 0.8) which is a short version of the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) was used to assess moderation of alcohol consumption.(83) It contains 4 items and a score of 0 for never",

1 for „Less than monthly“, 2 for „Monthly“, 3 for „Weekly“ and 4 for „Daily or almost daily“ was given.

3.14. Data processing and analysis

Data checked and cleaned after entered in to KOBO tool box, then imported to SPSS version 27.0 software for analysis. Incomplete and inconsistent data excluded from the analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the data. The results of the descriptive statistics were expressed as percentages and frequencies. Associations between independent and dependent variables were analyzed first using bi-variable analysis to identify factors which were associated with the outcome variable. Those variables which were found to have an association with the outcome variable at $P < 0.25$.(84) Were entered to multi-variable logistic regression to test for independent association. The magnitude of the association between the different independent variables in relation to dependent was measured using odds ratios and 95% confidence interval (CI) and P values below 0.05 were considered to be statistically significant.

3 .15. Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from Research Review Board of Karvard College. Official letters of support was obtained from public health department of Karvard College and was given to Addis Ababa City Administration health Bureau and then the official letter was given to all the three selected public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau. On the data collecting tool itself, the first page of the questionnaire was provide full information to the study participants regarding the purpose, nature of the research, beneficence, maleficent and then written Consent was obtained from each participant. Participation to the study was on voluntary basis, and participants were informed about their right not to participate in the study or withdraw at any time. Moreover, privacy and confidentiality of information was kept properly and names were not recorded.

3.16. Result dissemination

The findings disseminated to Karvard College Public Health Department using hard copy. The document will also be submitted to governmental and non-governmental stakeholders such as Addis Ababa health bureau serving on nutrition program. Finally; it will be submitted for publication.

4. RESULT

4.1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

Out of the total patients who were presented with musculoskeletal pain at the 3 hospitals during the study period, 385 eligible clients were included in the study, with response rate of 100%. Analysis was made based on the 385 completed questionnaires. The study consisted of 195 (50.6%) males which was almost equal to females. Among the female participants only less than half of them, 59(31.1%) and 38(29%) were pregnant and lactating respectively. The majority of participants were married, 240 (62.3%), the mean age of the respondents was 40.14(25.81, 54.47) years and lived in urban areas, 338 (87.8%) respectively. Additionally most of them had attained college or university-level education, 175 (45.5%) and governmental employee 129 (33.5%) with monthly income majorly, 234 (60.8%) earning between 5,000–20,000 Ethiopian birr.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS OLDER THAN OR EQUAL TO 18 YEARS PRESENTED WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL PAIN AT PUBLIC HOSPITALS UNDER ADDIS ABABA CITY ADMINISTRATION HEALTH BUREAU, ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA, 2025 (N=385)

Variables		Frequency n=385	Percent
Age	18-40	234*	60.8
	41-60	102	26.5
	>60	49	12.7
Sex	Female	190	49.4
	Male	195*	50.6
Marital status	Single	83	21.6
	Married	240*	62.3
	Divorced	34	8.8
	Widowed	28	7.3
	Can't read and write	31	8.1
Educational status	Read and write	69	17.9
	Primary	40	10.4
	Secondary	70	18.2

Occupational status	College/University	175*	45.5
	Unemployed	100	26
	Gov't employee	129*	33.5
	Private employee	70	18.2
	Private business	76	19.7
	Retired	10	2.6
Income	<5000	121	31.4
	5000-20000	234*	60.8
	>20000	30	7.8
Residency	Urban	338*	87.8
	Rural	47	12.3
Pregnancy	Yes	59	31.1
	No	131*	68.9
Lactation	Yes	38	29
	No	93*	71

*=Dominant number in the category of variable

4.2. PREVALENCE OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY

Among the 385 adult respondents (≥ 18 years) seen for musculoskeletal pain at public hospitals under the Addis Ababa City Administration Health Bureau in 2025, the overall prevalence of vitamin D deficiency was found to be 68.1% (95% CI: 63.1%–72.7%), whereas only 31.9%

(95%CI: 27.3%–36.9%) of respondents were classified as sufficient with vitamin D.

FIGURE 3: PREVALENCE OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AMONG RESPONDENTS OLDER THAN OR EQUAL TO 18 YEARS PRESENTED WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL PAIN AT PUBLIC HOSPITALS UNDER ADDIS ABABA CITY ADMINISTRATION HEALTH BUREAU, ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA, 2025 (N=385).

3. Personal characteristics of participants

Among the 385 adult respondents presenting with musculoskeletal pain, a majority 279 (72.5%) had daily sunlight exposure of 30 minutes or more. The use of sunscreen was reported by 90(24.7%) of participants and 116(30.1%) of respondents had comorbidities. In terms of knowledge about vitamin D, 168(43.6%) had good knowledge. Concerning dietary habits, 234(60.8%) consumed vitamin D-rich foods such as fish, milk, or eggs. And 64 (16.6%) reported taking vitamin D supplements. Only 30(7.8%) , 31(8.1%), 111(28.8%), 62(16.1%), 113(29.4%), and 140(36.4%) of respondents were on HAART ,used antiepileptic medications, reported using proton pump inhibitors, smokers, consumed alcohol and engaged in regular physical exercise respectively.

TABLE 2: Personal characteristics of respondents older than or equal to 18 years presented with musculoskeletal pain at public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2025 (n=385).

Variables		Frequency n=385	Percent
Sunlight exposure	< 30 minutes	106	27.5%
	>= 30 minutes	279*	72.5%
Use of sunscreen	Yes	90	24.7%
	No	295*	75.3%
Comorbidities	Present	116	30.1%
	Absent	269*	69.9%
Knowledge about vitamin D	Good	168	43.6%
	Poor	217*	56.4%
Consumption of fish, milk or egg	Yes	234	60.8%
	No	151	39.2%
Vitamin D supplement	Yes	64	16.6%
	No	321*	83.4%
Use of HAART	Yes	30	7.8%
	No	355*	92.2%
Use of antiepileptic	Yes	31	8.1%
	No	354*	91.9%
Use of proton pump inhibitors	Yes	111	28.8%
	No	274*	71.2%
Smoking	Yes	62	16.1%

	No	323*	83.9%
Alcohol	Yes	113	29.4
	No	272*	70.6
Exercise	Yes	140	36.4%
	No	245*	63.6%

4. Factors associated with vitamin D deficiency

After bivariate and multivariate binary logistic regression was done for each variables and for all variables with $p < 0.25$ respectively. Age, Residency and marital status (being single and widowed) of respondents were found to be significantly associated ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$) with prevalence of vitamin D deficiency. Respondents aged above 60 years were 4 times more likely to have vitamin D deficiency compared to those aged 18–40 years (AOR = 4.412, 95% CI: 1.745–11.154). Respondents living in urban were 3.58 times more likely to be vitamin D deficient compared to residents rural areas (AOR = 3.580, 95% CI: 1.288–9.949). Respondents who were single and widowed were 70% (AOR=0.302, 95% CI: 0.111, 0.826) and 80 % (AOR=0.190, CI: 0.053, 0.680) less likely to develop vitamin D deficiency as compared with widowed.

TABLE 3: shows the demographic, personal and behavioral factors associated with vitamin d deficiency among respondents older than or equal to 18 years presented with musculoskeletal pain at public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration health bureau, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2025 (n=385).

Variables	Vitamin D status		COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)
	Sufficient N (%)	Deficient N (%)		
Age in years				
18-40	179(76.5)	55(23.5)	1.00	1.00
41-60	62(60.8)	40(39.2)	2.100(1.274-3.459)	1.716(0.936,3.146)
>60	21(42.9)	28(51.7)	4.339(2.285-8.241)	4.412(1.745,11.154)**
Marital status				
Divorced	17(50.0)	17(50.0)	1.00	1.00

Married	158(65.8)	82(34.2)	0.519(.052,1.070)	0.429(0.181,1.017)
Single	66(79.5)	17(20.5)	0.258(0.109,0.607)	0.302(0.111,0.826)**
Widowed	21(75%)	7(25%)	0.333(.112,0.989)	0.190(0.053,0.680)**
Education				
College-university	132(75.4)	43(24.6)	1.00	1.00
Illiterate	21(67.7)	10(32.3)	1.462(0.639,3.346)	0.413(0.128,1.332)
Primary	25(62.5)	15(37.5)	1.842(0.890,3.810)	1.345(0.567,3.192)
Read and write	37(53.6)	32(46.4)	2.655(1.479,4.766)	1.188(0.216,6.533)
Secondary	47(67.1)	23(32.9)	1.502(0.820,2.754)	1.324(0.619,2.832)
Occupational status				
Governmental employee	91(70.5)	38(29.5)	1.00	1.00
Private business	55(72.4)	21(27.6)	0.914(0.487,1.716)	1.186(0.554,2.536)
Private employee	49(70.0)	21(30)	1.026(0.543,1.939)	1.816(0.851,3.877)
Retired	6(60)	4(40)	1.596(0.426,5.980)	1.188(0.216,6.533)
Unemployed	61(61.0)	39(39.0)	1.531(0.882,2.659)	1.324(0.619,2.832)
Income				
<5,000	70(57.9)	51(42.1)	1.00	1.00
5,000-20,000	168(71.8)	66(28.2)	0.539(0.341,0.854)	0.823(0.436,1.553)
>20,000	24(80.0)	6(20.0)	0.343(0.131,0.900)	0.432(0.128,1.455)
Residency				
Rural	41(87.2)	6(12.8)	1.00	1.00
Urban	221(65.4)	117(34.6)	3.618(1.492,8.770)	3.580(1.288,9.949)**
Sunscreen				
No	185(63.8%)	105(36.2)	1.00	1.00
Yes	77(81.1)	18(18.9)	2.888(1.580,5.277)	0.588(0.289,1.197)
Knowledge				
Poor knowledge	7(9.8)	57(16.6)	1.00	1.00
Good knowledge	64(90.2)	286(83.4)	0.505(0.322,0.790)	0.666(0.372,1.192)
Comorbidity				

No	188(69.9)	81(30.1)	1.00	1.00
Yes	74(63.8)	42(36.2)	1.317(0.832,2.086)	1.459(0.777,2.738)
Smoking				
No	210(65.0)	113(35.0)	1.00	1.00
Yes	52(83.9)	10(16.1)	0.357(0.175,0.730)	0.404(0.138,1.186)
Alcohol				
No	175(64.3)	97(35.7)	1.00	1.00
Yes	87(77.0)	26(23.0)	0.539(0.326,.892)	0.972(0.490,1.930)
Exercise				
No	160(65.3)	85(34.7)	1.00	1.00
Yes	102(72.9)	38(27.1)	0.701(0.444,1.106)	1.544(0.816,2.922)
BMI				
<18.5	109(76.2)	34(23.8)	1.00	1.00
18.5-24.9	20(66.7)	10(33.3)	1.603(0.684,3.755)	1.597(0.587,4.342)
>24.9	133(62.7)	79(37.3)	1.904(1.184,3.062)	1.356(0.777,2.365)

*AOR= statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

5. DISCUSSION

This study assessed the prevalence and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency (VDD) among adults with musculoskeletal pain in selected public hospitals in Addis Ababa. The prevalence of VDD was found to be 68.1%, markedly higher than the global pooled estimate of 15.7% (6) and the African pooled prevalence of 17.3% (7). Although studies suggest 30–80% deficiency in pain-related subgroups (35), the magnitude observed here is striking and likely reflects both the study population and contextual factors of urban living. The result is in line with Ethiopian studies, which report adult prevalence between 50–70%, with especially high rates in urban areas, such as 39% among pregnant women in Sodo (23) and 96% among multiple sclerosis patients in Addis Ababa (11). These findings reinforce that VDD is a critical public health problem in Ethiopia despite abundant sunlight.

Several factors were significantly associated with VDD. Older adults (>60 years) were more than four times as likely to be deficient compared to those aged 18–40 (AOR = 4.412, 95% CI: 1.745–11.154), consistent with evidence of reduced cutaneous synthesis and outdoor activity with age (19). Urban residents had over three times the odds compared to rural dwellers (AOR = 3.580, 95% CI: 1.288–9.949), echoing reports linking city life, indoor work, and pollution with limited sun exposure (4). Marital status also showed an association: divorced participants had higher odds of deficiency, whereas single and widowed individuals were significantly less likely (AOR = 0.302 and 0.190, respectively), though evidence for this relationship is limited and requires further study (25,26).

The high prevalence of deficiency among patients with musculoskeletal pain carries major clinical implications. Vitamin D is essential for calcium absorption, bone health, and muscle function, and its deficiency increases risks of osteomalacia, fractures, and chronic pain. These findings highlight the need for routine screening and supplementation among patients presenting with musculoskeletal pain. On a public health level, interventions should prioritize awareness, safe sun exposure, and support for high-risk groups such as older adults and urban residents. This study thus provides context-specific evidence from Addis Ababa and calls for urgent strategies to reduce the burden of vitamin D deficiency.

6. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATION

Strengths

The study employed a systematic random sampling method, enhancing representativeness, and used a robust sample size of 385, calculated with prevalence and non-response adjustments to ensure statistical power. Data quality was strengthened through trained data collectors and a pre-tested questionnaire.

Limitations

Being cross-sectional, the study can only show associations, not causality. Reliance on secondary data for serum vitamin D levels may have introduced inconsistencies due to laboratory variations across hospitals, possibly affecting prevalence estimates and associations. Self-reported data on lifestyle factors risk recall and social desirability bias. Although multivariable analysis was performed, unmeasured confounders such as genetics, specific clothing, or detailed medication use may still influence results. Generalizability is limited, as the study only included patients with musculoskeletal pain from selected Addis Ababa public hospitals. Finally, seasonal variation in UVB exposure was not analyzed, which could mask temporal patterns in vitamin D deficiency.

7. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that vitamin D deficiency is highly prevalent among adult patients with musculoskeletal pain in public hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Advanced age, and urban residency were found to be significant factors associated with this deficiency, along with marital status (being single or widowed compared to divorced). The findings underscore the critical need for increased awareness, routine screening, and targeted interventions for vitamin D deficiency, especially in older adults and urban dwellers, to improve musculoskeletal health and overall well-being.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Develop and implement public health programs focused on vitamin D awareness, particularly targeting urban populations and older adults in Addis Ababa. Consider food fortification strategies and educational campaigns on safe sun exposure and dietary sources of vitamin D.

Incorporate routine screening for vitamin D deficiency in adult patients presenting with musculoskeletal pain, especially those who are older or reside in urban areas. Provide appropriate guidance on supplementation, diet, and lifestyle modifications.

Conduct longitudinal studies to establish causal relationships between identified factors and vitamin D deficiency. Further research is needed to explore the specific reasons behind the association with marital status. Investigate the impact of seasonal variations on vitamin D levels and explore the effectiveness of various intervention strategies in the local context.

9. REFERENCES

1. Amrein K, Scherkl M, Hoffmann M, et al. Vitamin D deficiency 2.0: Worldwide Status. *Eur J Clin Nutr.* 2020;74(11):1498–513.
2. Cui A, Zhang T, Xiao P, et al. Global and Regional Prevalence of Vitamin D Deficiency, 2000–2022. *Front Nutr.* 2023;10:1070808.
3. Mogire RM, Mutua A, Kimita W, et al. Prevalence of Vitamin D Deficiency in Africa: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2019;7(11):e1345–55.
4. Al-Hetar MAMY, et al. Prevalence and Predictors of Vitamin D Deficiency in Yemen. *J Angiother.* 2024;8(11):1–9.
5. Stuhldreher KYZ, Forrest WL. Prevalence and Correlates of Vitamin D Deficiency in US Adults. *Am J Med.* 2011;31(1).
6. Nyangahu R, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency and Cardiometabolic Risks Among Healthcare Workers, South Africa. *BMC Public Health.* 2024;23:456.
7. Soubgui AFM, et al. Determinants of Vitamin D Deficiency in Adults, Cameroon. *Heliyon.* 2024;10(3):e24926.
8. Reverzani C, Zaake D, Nansubuga F, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency in Pregnant Women, Uganda. *BMJ Open.* 2025;15(1):e089504.
9. Guta Zenebe. Vitamin D Levels in Patients with Non-Specific Neuromuscular Pain in Ethiopia. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2020;30(3):337–46.
10. Ayele BA, et al. Serum Vitamin D Among Multiple Sclerosis Patients in Addis Ababa. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2020;30(4).
11. Haile DT, Damote TT, Sadamo FE, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency in Pregnant Women, Sodo Town, Ethiopia. *PLOS ONE.* 2022;17(12):e0279975.
12. Tessema B, Moges F, Habte D, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency Among Pulmonary TB Patients, Northwest Ethiopia. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2017;16(36).

13. Teklehaimanot WZ, Kitawu LD, Tesfaye T, et al. Sunlight Exposure Practice Among Mothers in Debre Berhan. *J Multidiscip Healthc.* 2021;12:507–17.
14. Lake EA, Demissie BW, Gebeyehu NA, et al. Mothers' Knowledge and Practice on Sunlight Exposure in Ethiopia: Systematic Review. *BMC Public Health.* 2022;22:213.
15. Phongamwong P, Chanwit C. Risk Factors for Vitamin D Deficiency in Chronic Pain Patients, Thailand. *J Pain Res.* 2023;9(1).
16. El-Sayed AM, Abbas FH, Mohamed SA. Risk Factors of Vitamin D Deficiency Among Egyptian Women. *BMC Public Health.* 2023;23.
17. Pigarova A, Dzeranova E, et al. Obesity, Diabetes, and Vitamin D. *Probl Endocrinol.* 2020;22(1).
18. Mohammad Ali, Zakir Uddin. Factors Associated with Vitamin D Deficiency in Musculoskeletal Pain. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* 2022;23(1).
19. Mayne P, Bradford D, Groves NJ, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency and Adverse Brain Outcomes. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2024.
20. Dey SK, Kumar S, Rani D, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency and Cardiovascular Health. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2024;64(28).
21. Magalhães PM, Cruz SP, Carneiro OA, et al. Vitamin D Inadequacy, Body Fat, and Muscle Mass in Women. *Nutrients.* 2024;16(9).
22. Khasanova SS, Asykpaeva A, Madjidova E, et al. Vitamin D Deficiency and Osteoporosis in the Elderly. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2023;11(1).
23. Xie Y, Farrell SF, Armfield N, Sterling M. Vitamin D and Musculoskeletal Pain in 349,221 UK Adults. *Pain.* 2024;25(9):104557.
24. Nasir S, Hussain M, Ali MYJ, et al. Vitamin D3 Levels and Back Pain. *J Adv Med Med Res.* 2024;36(10).

25. Montemor CN, Fernandes MTP, Marquez AS, et al. Vitamin D and Severity of Knee/Hip Osteoarthritis. *Nutrients*. 2025;17(3).
26. Holick MF, Binkley NC, Bischoff-Ferrari HA, et al. Evaluation and Prevention of Vitamin D Deficiency. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2011;96(7):1911–30.
27. World Health Organization. Vitamin D Supplementation in Infants. WHO; 2016.
28. World Health Organization. Global Solar UV Index: A Practical Guide. WHO; 2022.
29. Hosmer DW, Lemeshow S, Sturdivant RX. *Applied Logistic Regression*. 3rd ed. Wiley; 2013.
30. Fast Alcohol Screening Test (FAST). Hodgson et al. 2002.